

CISUFLO: Circular Sustainable Flooring

*Ine De Vilder, ivi@centexbel.be, Centexbel, Ghent, Belgium
Luca Bertamini, luca.bertamini@aquafil.com, Aquafil S.p.A., Arco, Italy
Madeira Scauri, scauri@enco-consulting.it, Enco S.r.l., Napoli, Italy
Marco De La Feld, m.delafeld@enco-consulting.it, Enco S.r.l., Napoli, Italy*

Summary

CISUFLO aims to setup a systemic framework for circular and sustainable ‘floor coverings’ (carpets (PA), resilient floor coverings (PVC) and laminates (wood)) and to minimise the total environmental impact of the sector. CISUFLO provides systemic innovations at technical, information and socio-economic level and performs 6 pilots to demonstrate their feasibility and value (future flooring, sorting, separation, laminate, vinyl, and textile flooring recycling). The basis for circularity is realising circular material streams. Circularisation will be realised via systemic innovations that deliver value along the chain: (i) manufacturing future flooring that is easier to remove, replace, repair & recycle, (ii) provide data via an integrated product information system. The final aim is to realize a sustainable competitive EU flooring manufacturing industry.

Riassunto

CISUFLO mira a creare un quadro sistemico per i “pavimenti” circolari e sostenibili (moquette (PA), pavimenti resilienti (PVC) e laminati (legno)) e a ridurre al minimo l’impatto ambientale complessivo del settore. CISUFLO fornisce innovazioni sistemiche a livello tecnico, informativo e socioeconomico, realizzando 6 progetti pilota per dimostrarne la fattibilità ed il valore (pavimentazione futura, smistamento, separazione, riciclaggio di pavimenti laminati, vinilici e tessili). La base della circolarità è la realizzazione di flussi di materiali circolari. Il nostro obiettivo è realizzare la circolarità attraverso innovazioni sistemiche che forniscano valore lungo la catena: (i) produrre pavimenti del futuro che siano più facili da rimuovere, sostituire, riparare e riciclare, (ii) fornire dati attraverso un sistema informativo di prodotto integrato. L’obiettivo finale è quello di realizzare un’industria manifatturiera competitiva e sostenibile per i pavimenti dell’UE.

1. Introduction

The European Green Deal [1], as launched by the Commission President Ursula von der Leyen in December 2019, has two main goals: to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and to create a Circular Economy in Europe, whereby resources are kept in circulation for as long as possible. The European flooring industry is working towards these goals by striving to increase the use of recycled content in products and to recycle more end-of-life flooring.

Against this background nineteen partners joined forces in 2021 in the European Horizon 2020 CISUFLO project [2], Circular Sustainable Floorings, which will last for 4 years. It aims to develop innovative circular products for the flooring industry, prompting, in the long run, the adoption of a circular economy model throughout the entire value chain and beyond. The project focuses in particular on carpets, laminate, and vinyl floor coverings. CISUFLO takes a holistic approach: looking at the ‘full product’ and the ‘full lifecycle’, thereby considering ‘full value chains’. The workplan foresees the implementation of six pilots focusing on manufacturing, sorting, separation, and recycling of floor coverings and on the scaling up of novel

technologies. An integrated product information system, to be aligned with upcoming digital product passports, will be introduced, providing the necessary data to each stakeholder along the value chain.

To make the shift to a circular economy, the flooring sector deals with multiple challenges. The product types are multiple and consist out of various raw materials (PVC, PA, PP, glass fibre etc.) and additives. Product lifetimes are very diverse: from 3-4 days (event carpet) to 20-40 years. The flooring sector is also linked to other sectors like construction and building, furniture, interior, plastics etc. and has a complex value chain.

2. Report

2.1 CISUFLO overall goals

The main goal of CISUFLO is to setup the systemic framework for circular and sustainable ‘floor coverings’ in EU and to minimise the total environmental impact of the sector. With ‘floor coverings’ textile floor coverings or ‘carpet’, resilient floor coverings or ‘vinyl’ and laminates are envisaged. The systemic framework will allow to align all the steps along the value chain to ensure maximum value retention of the products and the materials for the whole system. At each step, technical feasibility, as well as socio-economic aspects, will be ensured. At full circular level, data management will be ensured by creating ePRODIS, an electronic product information system. The impact of the developed products and processes will be evaluated using Lifecycle assessment (LCA) and Techno-economic assessments (TEA). An overview of the main activities, pilot 1 up to 6, is visualised in figure 1.

Fig. 1 – Overview CISUFLO

2.2 Pilot 1 – Circular floor coverings (CFC)

In order to technically realise CFC, there do exist single activities. But a harmonised, overall approach covering design, material and manufacturing is missing. Up to 80% of products’ environmental impacts are determined at the design phase, so concepts like Design for longevity, Design for disassembly and Design for recycling have to be taken into account. In order to

facilitate recycling, multi-material floor coverings are being redesigned using only one type of material (see figure 2 left).

For carpets, the focus lies on PA6, as this can chemically be recycled by Aquafil. The piles will be bonded using a thermofusion process. Further, if the mono-material concept would not be technically feasible, the implementation of separation layers is being assessed, which are triggering at end-of-life (see figure 2 right).

Fig. 2 – Overview concepts carpets: **Left**) Mono-material concept: A) PA6 piles, B) primary backing PA6, C,) thermofused piles, D,) secondary backing PA6. **Right**) Separation layer concept: A) PA6 piles, B+C,) primary backing PA6 with thermofused piles, C,) separation layer, D,) conventional secondary backing

Cushion vinyl has also a complex multi-layered structure and is not designed for recycling, hence it mostly ends up being incinerated or landfilled. Therefore, redesigning of the product is crucial to augment recycling rates.

As the CFC will be linked to an electronic database, a study is being conducted to find the most optimal tagging option. By reading out this tag, the necessary data (e.g. technical performance, material composition, maintenance, dismantling and collection procedure etc.) will be provide to relevant stakeholders.

2.3 Pilot 2 - Sorting

Current waste material sorting methods are well described [3,4]. The case studies focus on the analysis of flows of substances of concern, but no specific example is reported for flooring materials. Many efforts have been made recently to identify various types of materials by artificial intelligence, typically for separation of waste material at municipal waste collection companies, but little is available in Bibliography regarding specific flooring material sorting. A conveyor belt system is being developed enabling the identification and sorting of different flooring products. Identification will be done using a VIS camera, followed by near infrared spectroscopy.

2.4 Pilot 3 – Separation

As flooring materials which are in use nowadays are not designed for recycling, a method to separate the different polymer materials at end-of-life needs to be researched. For this purpose, the PolySep process [5] will be investigated. It is a solvent-based delamination/separation method. The solvent does not dissolve, but is absorbed within the materials. The material fibres are then blasted out with steam, and finally separated by air classifier. The separation of standard material combinations such as PA6/PP, PA6/latex, PVC/glass fibre etc. will be investigated. A pilot-scale plant is being implemented (see figure 3).

Fig. 3 – PolySep process (Pilot 3) diagram

2.5 Pilot 4 – Laminate recycling

Currently, laminate flooring is not recycled, but used as biomass fuel. The high-density fibre board (HDF), the baseboard of the product, is the main part of a laminate flooring (see figure 4). This HDF layer is composed of more than 80% wood fibres, which are bound together by resin or glue.

Fig. 4 – Composition of a typical laminate flooring: 1) Transparent wear resistant overlay; 2) Decor layer; 3) High Density Fibre Board (HDF); 4) Backer layer.

As laminate is mainly installed floating with a click system, waste streams are not polluted after removal when collected separately, and hence allow easy recycling at end-of-life. Several techniques have been studied by Unilin and finally a steam defibering process has been found most appropriate to convert end-of-life MDF/HDF containing products such as laminate flooring [6]. After intensive lab testing, a pilot plant has been built to demonstrate the feasibility of the technology. This pilot (design capacity 1.5 ton/hour) shows the potential of the process and is being operated currently on a daily basis in order to find the best process settings. The goal is to meet the requirements in terms of capacity of the process and degree of defibration, when using laminate flooring as an input material. The setup of the process has been done based on uncoated MDF/HDF. Using this kind of raw material, the process yields above 95% of good fibers when the input MDF is based on (melamine)urea-formaldehyde glues and with a capacity above 1 ton per hour. These produced recycled fibers are then used in replacement of virgin fibers in the MDF/HDF production line, without impacting the quality of the newly produced MDF/HDF. The next steps in the process are now focusing on further optimization of the process towards higher yield and lower energy costs and investigate the influence of the presence of coatings and the use of different types of (biobased) glues.

2.6 Pilot 5 – PVC recycling

Luxury vinyl tiles (LVT) are a very good example of a product that fits currently already very well the CFC: it can already be made with over 50% recycled post-industrial and post-fabrication PVC, but the current waste stream is too small to guarantee sufficient sourcing for LVT production. The tile itself can be recycled but only limited end-of-life LVT is already available. As it is a strongly growing market segment, the bottleneck is to provide sufficient additional recycle source, hence the use of recycled material coming from old window profiles is being investigated for LVT production. The potential to also use this specific recycle stream in cushion vinyl is also being assessed. So far, it is clear that virgin and recycle PVC powder behave differently when adding them to paste formulations. The differences between the virgin and recycle PVC powder are being mapped. It also has an influence on the foaming behaviour of the PVC, as can be seen in figure 5, so optimisation is needed.

Fig. 5 – Foamed PVC layer: Left) Reference, no recycle; Middle) 3 wt% recycle; Right) 12 wt% recycle

Next to the incorporation of recycled content, the recyclability of standard cushion vinyl will be assessed by using e.g., the PolySep process (described in section 2.4).

2.7 Pilot 6 – Circular carpet

Choosing the example of PA carpet, this pilot connects the outcomes of pilots 1, 2 and 3 (see sections 2.2 up to 2.4) to a material circle. This circle will cover the production step, the use phase and end-of-life with sorting and separation of flooring waste, as well as PA6 recycling. The completion of the cycle will be demonstrated by reintroducing recycled polymers (PA and PP) into the production step. The focus during the simulated use-phase will be on innovative installation materials to ensure easy removal and to demonstrate extension of the service lifetime via improved cleaning & maintenance, enabled by information provided via ePRODIS.

The full circularity of PA carpets will be demonstrated at industrial pilot scale. Different carpet types like residential broadloom, office carpet tiles and dust control mats will be investigated. The process will include yarn and carpet production, installation, service lifetime simulation, removal, sorting, separation, and recycling of the components.

As the possibility of carpet recycling, and its costs, will be determined by the separation methods identified. This will also define the route for improvements, through a specific eco-design in the carpet design phase.

CISUFLO will investigate both the mechanical separation, currently the main option at industrial level (ACR plant, Slovenia and USA, by Aquafil), and create the know-how already on a pilot scale for the solvent-based separation (PolySep Process).

On top, carpet recycling economics will be linked to the possibility to recover value also from the non-pile part (like NBR rubber, bitumen, PO, PVC, PP, PE, etc.) by creating connections within the world of material circularity.

3. Conclusions

According to Jane Gardner, Managing Director of the European Resilient Flooring Manufacturers Institute, and sustainability expert, collaboration and cooperation between companies, across sectors and across borders, is the best way to secure meaningful sustainability

improvements. This statement is completely in line with the European CISUFLO project, involving a diversity of partners, all with their specific knowledge.

Not only the technical challenges of redesigning floor coverings to be circular, and incorporating recycled content, are considered, the whole value chain is scrutinized. Other important aspects are how to collect the waste, logistics, circular business models, environmental impact, and cost of recycling processes etc.

As standardisation will play a huge role in the development of a circular economy, one should take the ongoing standardisation activities into account from the early development phase, so a liaison was established with CEN/TC 134 – Resilient, textile, laminate, and modular multilayer Floor Coverings – to align the CISUFLO developments with upcoming circular economy standards like the product passport.

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[2] www.cisuflo.eu

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